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A visual method for comparing article-level clustering approaches

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Introduction

Bibliometrics and scientometrics have used various approaches for clustering or grouping publications. Different approaches aim to capture the epistemic diversity of a research object, i.e., the diversity of empirical objects, methods, problems, or approaches to solving them (Glaser et al, 2015). Given that different meaningful and legitimate perspectives are possible, no single method can be more correct than another, but one method may be more suited to answering a particular question than another (Glaser et al, 2017; Hecking and Leydesdorff, 2018). Selecting a suitable method for a research project is important. Thus, comparisons are needed to learn about the differences between approaches. One can learn about the differences between approaches by applying the approaches to the same data set and comparing the outcomes.

However, previous comparative studies either only describe the differences between results, or only explain general reasons for differences. There is a lack of understanding of how differences between results can be attributed to specific properties of approaches used. We propose a visual method for comparing clustering approaches that aims to overcome the above limitations.

In this study, we compare article-level clustering method (AC) and the most popular method of topic modelling, i.e. Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA). Because they are two widely used methods in the field of scientometrics and haven't been compared yet. We build an overlay map of these two approaches. This map intuitively shows the relations between clusters and topics, including the one-to-one, and one-to-many relations between clusters and topics. It also shows clusters and topics that do not have any relations. These corresponding relations reflect how the different properties of the two approaches affect their results. We take cardiovascular disease (CVD) as a case study. Our work can help to understand how different approaches lead to different results, thus facilitating the selection of a suitable approach for practical applications.

Data

The dataset includes 433,642 cardiovascular publications (i.e., articles, letters, notes, and reviews) from 2010 to 2020, identified as described by [Gal et al. \(2015\)](#). The data were obtained from the in-house version of the Web of Science (WoS) database, updated until week 13 in 2020, at the Center for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University.

Methods

We apply the LDA and AC to identify topics and clusters, respectively, and we then construct an overlay map showing the relations between the topics and the clusters. There are three steps to construct an overlay map.

Step 1: Getting the document to the topic matrix. We train the LDA model of Gensim library to process titles and abstracts of retrieved documents, then we get the document to the topic matrix. We use Q_{ti} to denote the probability that document i belongs to topic t .

Step 2: Getting the document to cluster matrix. We link retrieved publications to the lowest level of classification system (micro-level research area) based on the AC proposed by [Waltman and van Eck \(2012\)](#) combined with the Leiden algorithm for network clustering ([Traag, Waltman & van Eck, 2019](#)), then we get the document to clusters matrix. We use R_{ci} to denote whether document i does ($R_{ci} = 1$) or does not ($R_{ci} = 0$) belong to cluster c .

Step 3: Getting the overlay map of LDA and AC. We build the overlay map based on these two matrices. We determine for each topic t and each cluster c the probability P_{ct} that a document belonging to topic t is in cluster c . Using n to denote the total number of documents, the probability P_{ct} is given by

$$P_{ct} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_{ti} R_{ci}}{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_{ti}}$$

We consider a topic t and a cluster c to be related if P_{ct} is greater than a threshold. We choose a value of 0.1 for this threshold. Hence, a topic t and a cluster c are considered to be related if $P_{ct} > 0.1$. Otherwise they are not related.

Results

From the overlay map, one can understand what aspects of the results of LDA and AC agree, and where they differ. The overlay map is available online at <https://bit.ly/3Aa2hzo>. Figure 1 shows how the overlay map can be used to find out with which clusters a specific topic is most strongly related. In Figure 1, colors indicate the relatedness value of topics and clusters given by P_{ct} . Clusters colored yellow have a value of P_{ct} of 0.1 or higher, while clusters colored blue have a value of P_{ct} of 0.02 or lower.

Figure 1. An example of the overlay map

The main contribution of this paper is the visual method for showing relations between topics identified using LDA and clusters identified using AC. This method yields the visualization presented in Figure 2. In this visualization, rectangles represent topics and circles represent clusters. The visualization also shows relations between topics and clusters. A topic may be related to multiple clusters, and likewise a cluster may be related to multiple topics. Stars represent topics (clusters) that do not have any relation with a cluster (topic).

Figure 2. Visualization of the relations between topics and clusters

In Figure 2, we can see epistemic themes identified by both methods (T11, C12), themes identified only by either LDA (T1, T4, T5) or AC (C95, C113), and the one-to-many relations between clusters and topics (T3 to C8, C29, C36, C90; C14 to T16, T25, T33). In terms of the one-to-many relations between clusters and topics, there are two opposite phenomena. One is that one topic corresponds to multiple clusters. The other is that one cluster corresponds to multiple topics. For instance, topic 3 is related to clusters 8, 29, 36, and 90. Conversely, cluster 14 is related to topics 16, 25, and 33.

The one-to-many relations provide in-depth insight into the differences in the results obtained from the different approaches. For example, cluster 14 corresponds to topics 16, 25, and 33. To further explore the reasons behind the situation, we learn clusters based on top 5 terms with the highest relevant score, which are extracted by the labeling approach proposed by Waltman and van Eck (2012). In more detail, C14 is related to medical imaging techniques, it contains “myocardial perfusion imaging”, “computed tomography”, “coronary computed tomography angiography”, and “coronary angiography”. That is because scientists cite documents that use similar materials, equipment, practical techniques, or tools of cited work, according to the analysis of citation behavior in Bornmann and Daniel, (2008). While in the LDA map, there are three different topics corresponding to C14. The LDA distinguishes these techniques with different functions for various diseases. For example, T16 talks about “magnetic resonance imaging” of nuclear medicine. It implies the semantic relation of terms could reflect the researcher’s interests (Hjørland, 2007).

Discussion and Conclusion

Understanding differences in the results obtained from different article-level clustering approaches is essential to select a suitable method for conducting a research project. The comparison is a source of understanding differences of approaches. However, previous comparative studies either only describe the differences between results, or only explain general reasons for differences. There is a lack of in-depth understanding of how different approaches affect results. We propose a visual method for comparing clustering approaches that aims to explore the in-depth reasons that approaches affect results.

We constructed an overlay map for comparing the results obtained from two widely used article-level clustering approaches in the field of scientometrics, namely LDA and AC. Despite their popularity, these methods haven't been compared yet. The overlay map intuitively shows the relations between clusters and topics, both one-to-one and one-to-many relations. It also shows clusters and topics that do not have any relations. The relations reflect the differences in the results obtained from the two clustering approaches. For instance, the one-to-many relations between clusters and topics reflect the different way of presenting knowledge organization (citation links and lexical similarities) of the same content by LDA and AC. It also reflects how the citation-based method (AC) and text-based clustering method (LDA) construct data and produce various results.

Our work provides a visual method for comparing article-level clustering approaches. It can help to understand differences in the results obtained from different approaches, thus facilitating their selection for practical applications. However, there are lots of possibilities for improving and extending the research. In this paper, we only compared two approaches. In the future, more approaches can be compared. In addition, based on understanding how different approaches' properties affect results, learning the merits and shortcomings of approaches, then linking approaches and decisions to the purpose of the analysis would be an important step forward.

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